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Santiago de Chile – the beautiful and modern capital of South America

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ABSTRACT

This report introduces the capital of Chile – Santiago de Chile, South America. A beautiful and modern city are the main features of this capital. Cheap hotels, wonderful restaurants, tasty food and cheap in bars. Full culture and high level of service to tourists. Main opinion: one can only envy such a capital. The trip took place in July 2005.

Keywords: Chile, Santiago de Chile, South America, modern city

INTRODUCTION

Returning from French Polynesia to Poland, I came to Chile, and more precisely to the capital of this country – Santiago de Chile, in July 2005 (Photos 1 & 3). It is cold in July in this country (in the capital) – 10-15 °C. The airport in Santiago de Chile is clean and tidy, it can be said to be sterile even compared to hospital hygiene (Photo 3). As soon as you leave the airport, you can immediately see the beautiful landscapes of the surrounding Andes Mountains (Photos 2, 4 & 5).

The capital city is beautiful, modern and what is interesting: this capital city is clean.

No visible rubbish on the streets is a very good feature of this city and country.

In Santiago de Chile, the capital of Chile, you can see many monuments (Photos 6-9) and many historic buildings (Photos 10-17).

In the background of the modern city of Santiago de Chile, you can see the ubiquitous snow-capped Andes Mountains, which adds the unique charm and beauty to this city (18-33).

Among the stately and architecturally beautiful modern buildings (Photos 9-39, 61-65, 71-82) one can sometimes observe the filming of a soap opera (Chilean telenovelas) (Photos 40 & 41).

There is already a different climate on the outskirts of Santiago de Chile. There is less car traffic here, it is quiet, and beautiful panoramic views of the Andes Mountains (Photos 42-60).

In the city of Santiago de Chile you can meet loud Australians in the restaurant, who listened to and sang Elvis songs on a video clip I launched (Photos 66-70).

I noticed a rather disturbing phenomenon there, namely very young people work in restaurants, bars or shops. In terms of age, it can be said that they are children. It turns out that all schools in Chile are paid. Not all children can learn because they simply cannot afford it. Therefore, they work at such a young age (Photos 14 & 65).

Santiago de Chile is located in a kind of valley between the mountains. Therefore, in the absence of winds, it is possible to observe smog from car exhaust fumes, which indicated high air pollution (Photos 11, 13, 20-22, 35-37, 72-75).

CONCLUSIONS

Santiago de Chile is a beautiful modern city with nice views of the Andes Mountains in the background. The city centre is clean and tidy. Restaurants are cheap here, with a high level of service. If there are no winds, there is air pollution in the form of smog.

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Appendix

Photo 1.

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Photo 3.

Photo 4.

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